

THE EFFECT OF SOME ETHLITIC PROTEINS ON WEIGHT, HORMONES AND EPIDYDYMIS OF MALE RATS

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Abstract: The present study mimic state of male individuals having sport nutrition without training, then to evaluate the effect of the most famous nutrition in Iraqi gems on the function and architecture of reproductive system in males of albino rats. Three types of nutrition were chosen for the experiment: hydrocarbonic Al-mass, proteinic isotope and createnine. Twenty male rats were divided into four groups: group (C) of control animals supplemented with normal feed and distailed water, group (P1) where animals feded concentration 0.627 gm/ml of al-mass with protein nature, group (P2) where animals feded kereatin with concentration 0.7 gm/ml, group (P3) where animals feded with isotop of carbohydratic nature with concentration 0.636 gm/ml.

The slides shows an effect of three types of nutreints on weight and architecure of epidydemis twards dysfunction and progression.

Introduction

Nonetheless, engaging in athletic competition might result in temporary harm to the system of reproduction as well as sexual dysfunction (genital discomfort, hypoesthesia of the genitalia, hypogonadism, DE, lowered sexual operate, etc.). or irreversible (hypogonadism, DE, etc.), through direct action (external sexual organs wounds, saddle-related diseases in cyclists, etc.) or indirect action (drug use, substance addiction, tension, exercise-related hypogonadism, etc.).

There are two types of nutrient: essential and non essential nutrients. Essentail or indisbansible nutrient has important consitueint in food that can prevent diseases and protect body from health problems, while nonessential or disbansible nutrient has bad effect on body health so it can be removed from diet whithout

any effect. In spite of these two concepts, but still nutrient important physiologically for body construction and health.

While they are another category, conditional essential nutrients. According to researches on animal and premature infants, body has the ability to build nutrients from precursors depending on its need and requirements. So that, Rudman and Feller (1986) suggested three standards that must be existed to prove a nutrient's conditional essentiality.

Materials and Methods

Twenty males of albino rats aged (11±4) weeks with weight rate (133) gm were used in the experiment. The animals were divided into four groups each group contains five rats, the feeding is by gavage tube:

Group (C): fed normal feed and distilled water.

Group (P1): fed concentration 0.627 gm/ml of al-mass with maize protein.

Group (P2): fed creatin with concentration 0.7 gm/ml.

Group (P3): fed with isotop of carbohydrate nature with concentration 0.636 gm/ml.

The duration of the experiment were thirty days, then the animal were weighted and sacrificed for collecting serum and sexual organs.

1- BioChemical test

At the end of the experiment, The animals were under anesthesia by inhaling chlorophorm then sacrificed for collecting blood serum and sexual organs. Serum samples were collected by using centrifuge 3000 rpm/15 minutes. Three sex hormones (FSH, Testosterone and estrogen) were measured in blood serum. The blood was collected by heart stabbing.

2- Histopathological preparation

Sexual organs were isolated and adipose tissues removed then let to dry. The organs were weighted by using sensitive balance. The weight depended on the reading of left and right parts of the same organ for more accuracy, then calculate the rate of each organ to the total body weight. Samples were kept in formalin 10% for preparing histopathological slides.

3- study of sperms parameters

Left epididymis tail was used for examining the progression of the sperms. The slides were prepared by preservation of samples in formaline 10% then undergone steps of preparing slides then stained by eosin-methylene blue stain. The slides were examined under power 100X and 400X.

Statistical Analysis:

The Statistical Analysis System- SAS (2018) program was used to detect the effect of difference factors in study parameters. Least significant difference –LSD test (Analysis of Variation-ANOVA) was used to significant compare between means in this study.

Results

➤ Weight of Body and Sexual Organs

Table(1) shows values of body weight after ending the period of experiment. The average of body weight before the experiment was (133) gm. Through the table(1), it is clear to notice declining in the weights of groups (P1, P2, and P3) significantly to (193.67 ±1.86) gm (183.33 ±12.01) gm and (196.67 ±10.14) gm respectively in comparison to control group (217.33 ±10.74) gm.

Table 1: Comparison between difference groups in body weight and blood sugar

Group	Mean ± SE	
	Body weight (gm)	Blood sugar (mg\dl)
Control	217.33 ±10.74 a	118.33 ±8.67
P1	193.67 ±1.86 ab	110.67 ±4.25
P2	183.33 ±12.01 b	115.67 ±1.20
P3	196.67 ±10.14 ab	122.00 ±4.35
LSD value	31.20 *	17.384 NS
P-value	0.0498	0.527
Means having with the different letters in same column differed significantly. * (P≤0.05), NS: Non-Significant.		

➤ Sexual Hormones Values

Table (2) shows increasing levels of testosterone in groups P1 and P2 nonsignificantly to(5.89± 4.59)IU/L in comparison to control group((5.23± 2.64)IU/L, while P3 of carbohydrate isotope has decreasing value of testosterone also non-significantly to(4.93± 2.88)IU/L in comparison to other groups.

Through the table, there is an increasing in Luteinizing hormone (LH) of P2(2.30± 0.70)IU/L non-significantly and higher than other groups, then P3 with value(1.67± 0.34)IU/L increased also significantly in comparison to control group(1.43± 0.57)IU/L. in opposite, P2 has decreased level in LH non-significantly to(1.20± 0.17)IU/L lower than other groups even lower than control group.

Follicle Stimulated Hormone (FSH) rises in values non-significantly in both P1 and P3 to(2.61 ± 1.38)IU/L and (2.63± 0.96)IU/L respectively in comparison to control group(1.43± 0.96) IU/L, while P2 poses nearly the same value (1.47± 0.89) IU/L to control group.

Table (2): Comparison between difference groups in Sex hormones (IU/Liter)

Group	Mean ± SE		
	Testosterone (IU/L)	LH (IU/L)	FSH (IU/L)
Control	5.23 ±2.64	1.43 ±0.57	1.43 ±0.96
P1	5.89 ±4.59	1.20 ±0.17	2.61 ±1.38
P2	5.89 ±4.59	2.30 ±0.70	1.47 ±0.89
P3	4.93 ±2.88	1.67 ±0.34	2.63 ±0.96
LSD value	12.373 NS	1.599 NS	3.482 NS
P-value	0.997	0.468	0.755
NS: Non-Significant.			

NS: Non-significant

4-

5- Epididymis

A-Control

B-Carbohydratic nutrition

C-isotope

D- Creatinine

Through the previous forms, its notice that there are an effect of epididymes structure and architecture. In comparison to control, the lobes of epididymes were elongated and the sperms were concentrated in the center of the lobes. In addition to the fact of the presence of inflammation in comparison to control.

Discussion

Through watching the movement of rats during experiment, it's noticed increasing their activity because of sport nutrients. Decreasing their weight may due to increasing body energy and their body activity in comparison to control group. According to research of -----, carbohydrates provides energy for body, as well as protein is required

Increasing levels of testosterone, LH, and FSH during puberty in males lead to testicular maturity and secondary features. Secondary characteristics of males and the production of testosterone are regulated by the same hypothalamic-pituitary axis. GnRH increases the release of FSH as well as LH from the pituitary, which in turn promotes the generation of testosterone from cholesterol. Then, testosterone signals the pituitary and hypothalamus to reduce their production of hormones through negative feedback regulation. Dihydrotestosterone (DHT), the active hormone, which is produced by the testes from testosterone. It is mostly (age related, but around 35%) linked to albumin and SHBG and delivered in blood to target tissues. Both cytoplasmic androgen receptors and nuclear are present in target organs.

In the research of Langan-Evan *et al.*(2022) on participant women having nutrient without training, the researcher found that these women have problems in menstrual cycle especially when contraceptives were used. And this agreed with the result of the present research but male rats.

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